

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11206633>

THE IMPORTANCE OF A SYNERGISTIC APPROACH IN THE FORMATION OF ECONOMETRIC SKILLS IN STUDENTS

Ravshanova Xurshida Makhmanazarovna
Ravshanova Mukhayyo Makhmanazarovna
University of Economics and Pedagogy

Annotation. *This article presents the basic concepts of the synergetic approach in the teaching of econometrics by the researcher and their interrelation, and explains the meanings of these concepts in accordance with the goals and objectives of the study.*

Keywords: *technology, synergetic approach, nonlinear, education, training, economics, method.*

In the last decade, a new direction of scientific research has appeared. This direction is synergy. Within the framework of synergetics, phenomena occurring in various natural systems such as the formation of spatial-temporal structures or spatio-temporal self-organization are studied in various natural systems, such as physical, chemical, biological, ecological, social.

B. B. Kadomtsev and Yu. A. According to Danilov, G. The term synergetics proposed by Haken, derived from the Greek word (senergina) - help, cooperation, focuses on the compatibility of the interaction of parts in forming a structure as a whole. G. Haken himself defines it as follows: "Synergetics is the study of systems composed of many sub-systems of different natures... we want to see how the interaction of these sub-systems leads to the emergence of spatial, temporal or spatio-temporal structures on a macroscopic scale." The moment of integrity in relation to synergetics S. P. Kurdyumov and G. G. Malinetsky notes: "Synergetics usually works with processes that acquire properties that none of the parts of a whole have."

Due to its interdisciplinarity, synergetics leads to a new constructive dialogue between experts from different academic disciplines. Synergetics is taking important steps towards the synthesis of science-based and humanities. Thus, as long as econometrics, in turn, is considered the result of an interdisciplinary approach to the study of economics and is embodied as a special "combination" of three components:

economic theory, statistics and mathematics, the use of synergistic methods in the process of teaching econometrics is not only possible, but also inevitable.

The role of synergy in education is two-fold. It can be about synergistic approaches to education, about synergistic ways of organizing the education and training process, and about teaching through synergism, synergistic knowledge transfer and dissemination. In the first case, synergetics is manifested as a method of education, and in the second case, as its content. The following synergistic methods of education are distinguished: independent education, non-linear conversation, evocative learning.

Self-organization is one of the important concepts of synergetics. In the educational aspect, this means self-education. It's no secret that good management is self-management. According to Daoist theory, a ruler who rules as little as possible is better. Regarding the system, it can be said that a teacher who teaches as little as possible, or rather gives a lesson, is a good teacher. The main thing is not to transfer knowledge, but to supplement knowledge and to acquire methods of self-learning, which quickly find their place in the branched system of knowledge. Self-organization plays a leading role in the process of teaching econometrics, because the number of hours allocated to classroom training in this discipline does not fully allow the student to master the required amount of material if he does not actively work independently.

The paradigm of self-organization or the synergetic paradigm brings forth a new interaction of man with nature. It also causes a person to establish a new relationship with himself and with other people. The nonlinear situation, the situation of bifurcation of evolutionary paths, or the instability of the nonlinear environment, the situation of its sensitivity to small influences is related to the uncertainty and possibility of selection. Making the choice of the next path, the subject is directed to one of the personal paths of the evolution of the complex system with which he enters the relationship, as well as to his valued advantages. He chooses a more acceptable path for himself. At the same time, it is one of the spectrum of ways determined by the internal properties of this complex system, that is, by one of the ways realized in it. Therefore, synergetics can be seen as an optimistic way of managing a non-linear (undisciplined, chaotic) situation.

A situation of non-linear (chaotic, undisciplined) communication arises during the study of practical methods of mathematics and statistics in economics. Economics is a complex, dynamic, multifaceted and evolving subject, which is why it is difficult to study. Both society and the public system change over time, laws change, technological innovations occur, so it is not easy to find invariants in this system. One of the practical tasks of econometrics is the construction of multivariate scenario

calculations for forecasting and analysis of the development of economic systems, which requires that it is reasonable to use synergetic methods in the educational process. From a synergistic point of view, the educational procedure, the student's relationship with the teacher, and the teacher's relationship with the student are shown as follows. This is not the transfer of knowledge from one head to another, the publicizing of ready-made truths, and not pulling. It is a non-linear (chaotic, undisciplined) situation of falling into a self-agreed tempo world as a result of open communication, direct and feedback, joint learning adventure, problem solving. The latter means that due to joint activity in such a situation, the teacher and the student begin to work at the same speed, live at the same pace..

The main problem is how to manage, how to give impetus to one of the paths of personal and acceptable development for a person with a small resonant influence, how to ensure self-directed and self-sustaining development. The problem is again how to curb chaos (the student's unorganized and spontaneous aspirations), not to repel it, but to give it a creative tone, turn it into a field, and give birth to sparks of innovation. A synergistic approach to learning consists of motivational or cooperative learning, self-awareness, or learning to collaborate with oneself and others. There are specific configurations of knowing, learning, and living situations. In order to act more effectively, it is necessary to act at the right time and in the right place. This idea does not lose its meaning in solving the problems of teaching any discipline, including econometrics. In the case of a synergistic approach, we are talking about resonant, topologically correct effects

Judging from the above-mentioned opinion, the use of the synergistic approach as a priority approach in the process of teaching econometrics is considered relevant and justified.

So, synergistics is a set of scientific views based on the recognition of the self-organization of the world, the eternal sequence of events in space and time, their interrelationship, and their existence based on the causal connections of certain systems. There are those who say that this doctrine is formed on the basis of dialectics and complements it with a complex of scientific views. Contrary to them, there are also those who believe that dialectics is no longer necessary, it should be replaced by synergistics.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

1. Юцявичене П. А. Теория и практика модульного обучения / П. А. Юцявичене. - Каунас: Швиеса, 1989. - 271 с.
2. Шермухамедова Н.А. “Фалсафа ва методологияси”- Университет, 2005.
3. Назаров Қ.Н. “Билиш фалсафаси” Т.: Университет, 2005.
4. Равшанова М. М. MATHEMATICAL METHODS IN ECONOMETRICS AS A TOOL FOR ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEMS //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 5-2. – С. 1036-1038.
5. Равшанова М. М. MATHEMATICAL METHODS IN ECONOMETRICS AS A TOOL FOR ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEMS //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 5-2. – С. 1036-1038.
6. Nabiev O. A. FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF REGULATION OF UNCERTAIN POPULATION EMPLOYMENT //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2019. – №. 10. – С. 530-535.
7. Maxmanazarovna, Ravshanova Muhayyo. "ECONOMETRIC MODELS, THE ESSENCE OF THEIR USE AND THE NEED FOR ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS." *Intent Research Scientific Journal* 2.6 (2023): 5-9.